

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. ethilla*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.299

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. ethilla*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.309

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

